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USING THE DIGITAL RESOURCES IN LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

This article considers the prerequisites for the personal and professional attributes of future specialists, very in demand after in today's society. It explores their advancements in language education, encompassing the integration of digital technologies and global computer networks. In point of fact, many internet networks and applications can help to attain heights in the field of teaching. Particularly, in article also considers the significance of a methodical selection of teaching aids to reach concrete aims set by teachers.

Key words: *Computerization, modern education, foreign languages, digital technologies, internet, selection of teaching.*

INTRODUCTION

In a time when information technology is developing at a rapid pace, society need aspiring professionals to be capable of independent knowledge acquisition and practical application in order to effectively handle a wide range of difficulties. Success

involves in sociability, collaborative possibility in varied scenarios, seeking resolution in conflict situations, critical and creative thinking, and the adept utilization of modern information technologies for problem-solving. It is imperative to consistently work toward improving one's cultural qualities. The growing of these skills and cognitive abilities among students is facilitated through the integration of active learning technologies into the educational process.

Presently, the fundamental criterion in choosing educational tools is attaining the specified proficiency levels in foreign languages. These levels of information exchange system, ensuring effectiveness in language education.

METHODS

Classes on language acquisition need to develop into interesting and fulfilling experiences that encourage true linguistic innovation. Students will only become enthusiastic, self-directed learners in these circumstances, developing their independence and drive to change to meet new curriculum requirements.

In the present era, computerization has affected every aspect of human activity, including science and education. The evolution of the Internet, along with the advent of numerous computer programs that aid in learning have significantly changed the way that foreign language education is conducted. As a result, efficiency has grown, speeding up the learning process and making interaction with real language sources easier.

Computer training programs offer several advantages over traditional teaching methods, primarily through direct audiovisual interactive engagement. Unite them with conventional teaching approaches in the classroom permits the development of diverse speech activities, understanding linguistic phenomena, shaping linguistic abilities, establishing communicative scenarios, automating language skills, and ensuring individualized learning. This approach increases students' independent work, enhances cognitive activity, motivation, and overall knowledge quality.

RESULTS

Computer communication technologies present a fresh way to put teaching methods into practice that encourage students' creative participation. Learners can actively participate through collaborative creative projects with students from different universities, as well as virtual debates on educational websites and topical forums. Consequently, the incorporation of modern information and communication technologies into the educational process emerges as a dynamic form of individualized learning.

Relying on N.K. Ryabtseva's words, the using of computer technology introduces innovation to the learning process, fostering motivation for effective self-discovery and self-improvement. This method makes lessons attractive, sincerely modern, and supportive of individualized learning. Additionally, it ensures objective and timely assessment and summarizing.

DISCUSSION

To maximize the effectiveness of applications and programs, it's important to ask "Why?" and "What is the major purpose of using computer technology in educational process?"

The reasons may differ:

- to better comprehension of the subject under study;
- increase learning time by motivating pupils to use educational programs and resources outside the classroom;
- to improve the effectiveness of the teachers' work;
- developing students' independence;
- enhancing computer performance;
- developing students' qualities such as determination to achieve results;
- increase students' motivation and etc.

Teachers commonly employ strategies of discussing new concepts and trends to motivate students when teaching foreign languages. The availability of personal

computers and digital gadgets with internet connection makes it easier for teachers to engage pupils in learning foreign languages via the internet.

CONCLUSION

In the current day, achieving a high-quality modern education requires the logical combination of traditional teaching methods with cutting-edge technologies. Educational digital technologies introduce fundamentally new methodological approaches in the general education system. Multimedia visualization is good for both teachers and students when used in the classroom. Students become active participants in the learning process because it gives them the freedom to choose how they interact with the contents, make use of interactive elements, and work with peers.

High-quality multimedia increases the flexibility of the learning process by taking into account students' varied interests, individual learning styles and speeds, also social and cultural variations.

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